

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Improving the electrochemical desalination performance of chloride-doped polyaniline activated carbon electrode by tuning the synthesis method

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Table S1. Mass yields of physical (Y_{Ph}) and chemical (Y_{Ch}) activations, and overall yield (Y_0).

Material	Y_{Ph} ^a	Y_{Ch} ^a	Y_0 ^b
CTAK*	-	0.16	0.08
CTAK	-	0.37	0.18
HTAC	0.93	-	0.38
HTAK	-	0.37	0.15
HTACK	0.93	0.37	0.14

Notes: ^a (g AC/g char); ^b (g AC/g PANi).

Table S2. CDI performance using different carbon electrodes.

Material	SSA_{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	NaCl (mg L ⁻¹)	Applied voltage (V) or density current (mA cm ²)	SAC (mg g ⁻¹)	OSR (mg g ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)	η (J mg ⁻¹)	Reference
Filtrisorb 400 AC ^a	700	585	0.4 mA cm ²	3.5	100	4.3	Chen et al. [1]
Nanoporous 3D- graphene	445	500	1.6 V	17.1	163	-	Shi et al. [2]
Sugar cane biowaste- derived AC	1172	600	1.2 V	22.8	607	-	Lado et al. [3]
Cotton-derived carbon sponge	2680	500	1.2 V	16.1	939	-	Li et al. [5]
Polyglycerol AC	1684	600	1.6 V	27.1	1070	2.6	Juchen et al. [6]
MSP20 AC ^b	2272	585	2.5 mA cm ²	11.2	1401	1.6	Kang et al.

Fig. S3. Schematic representation of chemical activation of the CT and CT* samples **(a)**, and chemical and physical activation of the HT samples **(b)**.

Fig. S4. Schematic representation of the electrode preparation procedure.

Fig. S5. **(a)** CDI cell used in this work (adapted from Zornitta et al. [10]), indicating the asymmetric configuration, and **(b)** experimental system. Source: [11], reproduced with authorization of Elsevier.

Fig. S6. (a) Turbostratic and graphitic carbon structures, and (b) XRD patterns of the activated samples.

Fig. S7. FTIR spectra of the hydrothermally carbonized/activated samples.

Fig. S8. XPS survey spectra for the CTAK*, CTAK, HTAK, and HTACK materials.

Fig. S9. Deconvoluted high resolution XPS C 1s spectra of CTAK* (a), CTAK (b), HTAK (c), and HTACK (d).

Fig. S10. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms **(a)** and pore size distributions **(b)** of the ACs. Inset: cumulative pore volume.

Fig. S11. Normalized salt adsorption **(a)** and desorption **(b)** concentrations, as a function of electroadsorption and desorption time, respectively. The lines represent the fits of the pseudo-first order models used to determine the kinetic constants of electroadsorption (k_e) and desorption (k_d).

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